

Development of Advanced Composite Fabrication for Aerospace Structures

Y. Satakanji, Y. Yamaguchi

Nagoya Aircraft Works, Mitsubishi Heavy Ind., Ltd., 10 Oye-cho, Minato-ku, Nagoya 455, Japan

ABSTRACT

Currently, practical applications of advanced composite materials to aerospace vehicles have been increasing and are being expanded from secondary structures to primary structures.

The object of this study is to establish manufacturing processes for advanced composite primary structural components. This paper presents manufacturing feasibility obtained as a result of fabrication tests of the structural components. These include four kinds of complex shape integrated structures and take advantage of the flexible moldability of graphite/epoxy advanced composite materials. One type of spar element, two types of skin-to-spars elements and one type of box model elements were selected as the structural component specimens. They were fabricated from graphite/epoxy prepregs using hand lay-up and autoclave cure with elastomeric tooling systems. The resultant fabricated elements showed no defects and had uniform qualities.

It has been established that the optimizations of the materials, tooling systems and curing cycles are important. In order to proceed, further studies on manufacturing developments of advanced composite materials for primary structures of aerospace vehicles must be made.

INTRODUCTION

Practical applications of graphite/epoxy composites, which have excellent specific strength and modulus, to aerospace structures have been increasing and are being expanded from secondary structures to primary structures.

The object of this study was to demonstrate the feasibility of the fabrication of graphite/epoxy aircraft primary structural components. The selected complex shapes, which included spars, ribs and skin-to-spar elements, took advantage of the flexible moldability of graphite/epoxy. The element fabrications were achieved by means of single step cocure fabrication methods.

There is no doubt that structural materials of light weight, high strength and modulus, and high durability are required for modern aircrafts. But, reductions of material cost with its collateral implications of resource conservation and energy saving cannot be ignored. The application of graphite/epoxy composites can provide this dual advantage when replacing the less strength efficient and more labor and energy intensive metal designs if the design and manufacturing techniques for composites can be mastered. These techniques are shown below:

- ① Arrangement of reinforcing fibers in the required quantity in the required positions and directions.
- ② Consideration of the fabricating processes such as materials, toolings and costs from the start of designing.
- ③ Fabrication of integral structures in order to reduce the number of parts and minimize joints and fasteners.

Optimization of the application of graphite/epoxy composites to primary aircraft structures will ultimately require the evolution of fabrication technology shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Evolution of Fabrication Process for Spars¹⁾

Examples of current used structure are the graphite/epoxy skin-honeycomb sandwich structure (Fig. 2), the aluminium spar reinforced with graphite/epoxy (Fig. 3) and adhesive bonded graphite/epoxy I beams (Fig. 4).

Fig.2 Graphite/Epoxy Skin Honeycomb Sandwich Structure²⁾

Fig.3 Aluminium Spar Reinforced with Graphite/Epoxy

Fig.4 Adhesive Bonded Graphite/Epoxy "I" Beams

TRIAL FABRICATION

Test Elements

The integral structural elements selected for trial fabrications were one type of spar elements, two types of skin-to-spar elements and one type of box model elements. All of them are representative components for wing and body structure of aircrafts and as such are objects for a common basis to establish the concept of fabricating processes.³⁾ The details of the test elements are shown in Figs. 5 to 8.

Fig. 5 Sine Wave Spar Element

Fig. 6 Skin/Spar Integral Structural Element

Fig. 7 Skin/Spars Integral Element

Fig. 8 Box Type Structural Element

Materials

The specifications and properties of the selected prepreg materials are shown in Table 1. The both prepregs have high strength graphite fibers and high performance four functional epoxy resins.

Table 1 Specification and Properties of Prepregs

Prepreg	Specification	Forms	Prepreg Property	Laminate Property
Unidirectional Graphite/Epoxy	M1540	341mm Wide Tape	Resin Content: 40% Volatile Content: 1% Nominal Thickness: 0.15mm/ply	Tensile Strength: 170kg ^f /mm ² Tensile Modulus: 14000kg ^f /mm ² Interlaminar Shear Strength: 10.9kg/mm ²
Woven Fabric Graphite/Epoxy	M1543	1m Wide Roll	Resin Content: 43% Volatile Content: 1% Nominal Thickness: 0.40mm/ply	Tensile Strength: 55kg ^f /mm ² Tensile Modulus: 7,180kg ^f /mm ² Interlaminar Shear Strength: 6.7kg ^f /mm ²

Fabrication Process

The structural elements of this study were fabricated using the process shown in Fig. 9. The process used hand lay up of the preregs and an autoclave cure which is the current industry standard. Special tooling described below was applied.

Fig. 9 Fabrication Process

Elastomeric Tooling

In order to fabricate the elements in a single cocure step, special tooling is required which has the ability to apply pressure evenly to the complex lay up. The physical properties of the selected elastomeric tooling materials are shown in table 2 and the process for tool manufacture is shown in Fig. 10.

Table 2 Properties of Elastomeric Tool Material

Material	Hardness	Strength	Modulus	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	Thermal Conductivity
Elastomer	Shore A 60	50kg/cm ²	1,100kg/cm ² Maximum Elongnation 200 %	1x10 ⁻⁴ / ^o C	3.0 Kcal/m.h. ^o C

Fig. 10 Process for Tools Manufacture

Pre-Bleeding

The lay up was debulked and prebled prior to final assembly on the lay up tool. This assured proper ply thickness and fiber volume fraction Vf. Fig. 11 shows the effects of this pre-bleeding.

Fig. 11 Effects of Prebleeding

Results

Figs. 12 to 15 show the results of this study. None of the elements had visual defects and were dimensionally correct. No occurrence of voids or cracks were detected. Uniformity of fiber distribution and VF (55-60 vol. %) were confirmed by samples taken from the final trim areas.

Fig. 12 Sine Wave Spar Element

Fig. 13 Skin/Spar Integral Structural Element

Fig.14 Skin/Spars Integral Element

Fig.15 Box Type Structural Element

FUTURE STUDIES

Items for future studies include;

- 1) Optimization of material selection and construction for tooling must be made. The use of other elastomers, low melting point metals and eutectic salts will be explored.
- 2) Optimization of prepreg selection and cure cycles must be made. The use of different fibers, different weaves and the study of the resin rheometric and gel characteristics will be explored.
- 3) Optimization of structural design will be made. The relationship between structures and materials with processability, strength, weight and cost will be explored.

REFERENCES

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